

Influence of Thiocompounds on the corrosion of Aluminium (3S) in local supply moving Water

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accepted 15 September 1973

ALUMINIUM and its alloys are extensively used for industrial and domestic purposes due to their cheapness and good resistant power towards organic acids and waters. Aluminium pipes carrying hard water often meet with sudden failures

The influence of thioacids and azoles was studied previously as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium and its alloys in different corrosive environments¹⁻⁵. Patel, *et al.* studied the effect of some known compounds towards the corrosion of brass at low flow velocity water¹. Corrosion of 3S aluminium in local supply water was studied by Pandya².

In the present investigation we are going to deal with the action of thioglycolic acid, diethiodiglycolic acid, 2-mercaptobenzoic acid, benzimidazole, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (2 MBT) and 2-benzimidazole thiol on the behaviour of aluminium immersed in low flow velocity water. The aim of our research work is to investigate the behaviour and action mechanism of the formerly cited inhibitors.

Experimental

i) Materials :

All chemical used as corrosion inhibitors were of BDH grade.

The chemical composition of 3S aluminium (22 S.W.G., $\frac{1}{2}$ hard) was as follows :

Al—97%, Cu—0.15%, Mn—1.0 to 1.5%, Zn—0.1%, Fe—0.75% and Si—0.6% (maximum).

ii) Analysis of supply water :

The composition of the water used for the present studies is given below.

CO₃⁻⁻—Nil, HCO₃⁻⁻—610; Cl⁻—530, SO₄⁻⁻—82; Na⁺—480, Ca⁺⁺—48, Mg⁺⁺—37ppm, SiO₂—Tr, Cu⁺⁺ < 0.02, TDS—1600 ppm and pH—7.6.

iii) Experimental method :

For the studies of the corrosion of aluminium in stagnant supply water specimens of 4×8 cm size were totally immersed in 500 ml of water while for the velocity studies 4×8 cm specimens were immersed in the water in a polyethylene tub (24×15×12 cm). The testing procedures to study the corrosion and its inhibition of 3S aluminium in low

flow velocity water were adopted as those described by Porter and Hadden⁶. The apparatus for the tests in slowly moving water is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

It was not possible to maintain with the equipment available an exact rate of flow of water. The rate of flow of water was measured every day and average rate was considered. The specimens were cleaned by chromic acid solution. Results of the corrosion of 3S aluminium in stagnant and moving conditions are given in Table 1. The percentage efficiencies of the inhibitors and weight loss data in presence of inhibitors are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—CORROSION OF 3S ALUMINIUM IN LOCAL SUPPLY WATER

(Stagnant condition)

Size of specimen : 4 × 8 cm		Temperature : 30° ± 2°	
Duration in days	Loss mg	Loss mg/dm ²	Loss mdd
15	13	2.03	1.35
30	25	39.0	1.30
45	38	59.4	1.32

Corrosion Rate :

Domestic waters as a general class present a very wide variety of environmental conditions both chemical and physical Constituents commonly found in the domestic water supplies may be classified as follows :

- 1) Dissolved gases like oxygen, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, etc.
- 2) Dissolved mineral constituents like calcium magnesium, sodium, heavy metals chlorides, sulphates, bicarbonates, silica etc.
- 3) Organic matter of animal, vegetable and waste materials.
- 4) Insoluble materials.
- 5) Microbiological forms like algae and bacteria.

Corrosion rate in stagnant condition is dependent upon diffusion and convection currents

NOTES

TABLE 2—3S ALUMINIUM (4×8 CM) IN LOCAL SUPPLY WATER WITH AND WITHOUT INHIBITOR

(Moving condition)

Name of inhibitor	Average rate of flow lit/hr.	Concentration of inhibitor (ppm)	Test Duration								
			15 Days			30 Days			45 Days		
			Loss mg	Loss mdd	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Loss mdd	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Loss mdd	Inhibition %
Blank	14.0	—	64.0	6.67	—	105.0	5.60	—	161.0	5.59	—
Thioglycollic acid		0.08	4.9	0.51	91	10.3	0.54	90	13.4	0.46	92
Blank	9.8	—	33.0	3.44	—	57.0	2.97	—	102.0	3.54	—
Dithio diglycollic acid		0.11	3.0	0.31	90	5.0	0.26	91	10.0	0.35	90
Blank	10.0	—	35.0	3.65	—	60.0	3.13	—	108.0	3.75	—
2-mercaptobenzoic acid		0.1	1.5	0.16	95	1.6	0.083	97	3.9	0.139	96
Blank	13.0	—	58.0	6.04	—	98.0	5.10	—	155.0	5.38	—
Benzimidazole		0.08	4.7	0.89	92	4.8	0.25	95	24.3	0.843	84
Blank	15.0	—	66.0	6.87	—	123.0	6.40	—	166.0	5.76	—
2MBT		0.075	2.1	0.22	97	2.8	0.15	98	3.7	0.13	98
Blank	18.0	—	82.0	8.54	—	144.0	7.50	—	285.0	9.89	—
2-Benzimidazolethiol		0.05	3.0	0.30	90	3.4	0.18	98	7.6	0.26	97

alone. However, the corrosion rate of 3S aluminium in stagnant condition is very less but a slight movement increases corrosion tremendously. Generally increased velocity increases corrosion rate by removal of protective corrosion products. The pattern of attack usually is of the form of localized pitting.

Water velocity influences corrosion in several ways. As a general, tendency towards deposit formation and associated corrosion varies inversely with flow rate. On the other hand, high velocity favour excessive turbulence, thereby promoting impingement and cavitation attack on irregular surfaces in the system. Besides increased velocity mostly increases corrosion rate by removal of protective layer of corrosion product by mechanical means.

Inhibitor efficiencies :

Sulphur containing organic compounds have been shown to have a high degree of inhibition property³. As S-containing groups of organic compounds are known to influence to a considerable extent the cathodic step in the corrosion reaction, studies of these compounds are both theoretical and practical interest.

Organic compounds like thioglycollic acid, dithio diglycollic acid, 2-mercapto benzoic acid, benzimidazole, 2 MBT and 2-benzimidazole thiol are found effective corrosion inhibitors for 3S aluminium in low flow velocity (9.8 to 18 lit/hr) water. Although 2 MBT and 2 mercaptobenzoic acid act as excellent corrosion retarders. In the presence of these inhibitors the plate remains very bright after cleaning. A protective film is formed on the plate surface which is adherent and tight.

These inhibitors are adsorbed on the plate forming a protective layer on the plate surface, hence corrosion particularly of pitting type is completely stopped. It is interesting to note that these substances are added in very minute quantities.

The efficiencies of these compounds are increased with increase in duration

Since the rate of flow was varied, it is not possible to decide between their relative efficiency. The inhibitors are however categorise in the following order :

Type	Inhibition %	Inhibitor
Excellent	>95	2-MBT, 2-Mercaptobenzoic acid.
Effective	<95	Thioglycollic acid, dithio diglycollic acid, Benzimidazole, 2-benzimidazole thiol.

Acknowledgement

Our thanks are due to late Dr. A. M. Trivedi (Professor of Chemistry, University School of Sciences) for the inspiring guidance in the work.

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